

AUTOMATIC PROBABILISTIC ANALYSIS OF ABNORMAL ADULT BRAIN SIGNAL

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Abstract

Electroencephalograph (EEG) signal is brain electrical activity and recorded from the scalp by using electroencephalogram. EEG reflects functional status of the brain. EEG signal has a unique contribution and meaningful to recognize the electrical function of the brain. This signal is interpreted visually by electroencephalographers (EEGers) to be used as one of diagnosis instrument for some diseases in the brain. The parameter of visual analysis for awake patients includes frequency, amplitude, and symmetry of background signal, distribution, morphology, and also reactivity. The normality or abnormality of signal could be determined based on these parameters. Unfortunately, the visual analysis has some weaknesses. First, it is the lack of reliability due to the various capability of EEGers. Secondly, if the spatial resolution of EEG increases, EEGers need more time to interpret the signal. Hence, an automatic analysis based on computer was developed to improve the scoring reliability and able to perform a fast calculation process for a large EEG data. In this work, we developed a probabilistic analysis method to justify the abnormality of EEG signal based on the quantitative parameters. This quantitative parameter estimation adopted from the method used by the clinicians for visual reading. However, the result of calculation could not be directly used to determine the abnormality of EEG signal. So, the probabilistic analysis was used with 14 features of the calculation result parameters on each 65 of normal and abnormal EEG data. The performance of the system for normality and abnormality were validated by 10-fold cross validation using discriminant analysis resulted 78.46% of accuracy. In conclusion, it could be said that features extraction adopted from visual analysis are able to distinguish between normal and abnormal in the clinical EEG signals.

DOI :

1. Introduction

Brain signal is a subject that still has a lot of mystery because it is nonstationary and very sensitive to the artefacts. Extracting information from brain signals is difficult. Several studies have been conducted to find the most effective way of interpreting brain signals through electroencephalography (EEG). In the diagnostic field EEG signal readings are carried out visually by certified clinicians. However, this method still has many disadvantages including lack of reliability because it really depends on the experience and ability of the interpreter [1] and is also time consuming.

Therefore the study on the automatic interpretation of EEG signals began to be developed. In general, there are two approaches in interpreting the EEG signals, which are deterministically

[2] – [6] or probabilistically using a machine learning [7] – [11]. The deterministic method is usually based on the calculation of adoption parameters from visual readings, while the probabilistic approach uses signal statistical calculations. But each of them has its own drawbacks, in the preliminary study of deterministic interpretation, there was inconsistencies in classification results. On the other side, classification alone could not produce a description of the signal altogether. Therefore, in this study, automatic interpretation is performed using quantitative parameters adoption of visual methods and machine learning as a classifier to simultaneously produce descriptions and impressions of the EEG signals.

2. Method

The outline of the method to classify EEG impression consists of pre-processing (BPF 0.1 – 30 Hz), signal segmentation every 5 second, features extraction, classification using machine learning, and generating impression as normal or abnormal EEG (see figure 1). The EEG signal was transformed to the frequency domain to calculate its power spectrum. The power spectrum was calculated by using the Welch method with a sliding window of 2 seconds and overlapping of 50%.

Figure 1. Framework algorithm to classify EEG abnormality.

2.1 Data Preparation

Raw EEG data was obtained from the Temple University Hospital (TUH) Corpus database (https://www.isip.piconepress.com/projects/tuh_eeg/). A total of 130 data were taken randomly with 65 normal and 65 abnormal data. The age range used was between 18 to 60 years. The analysis was performed on 16 channels EEG (Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, C3, C4, P3, P4, O1, O2, F7, F8, T3, T4, T5, T6), using average reference (AR) montage. For the distribution of age and gender patient data is represented in figure 2.

2.2 Feature Extraction

The features used in this classification are based on quantitative parameters calculated from EEG signal power.

1. Background Rhythm Existence

Existence is a calculated parameter to judge the presentation of background rhythm compared to others. In awake patients, background rhythm considered as posterior dominant rhythm (PDR). The calculation is done by comparing the maximum signal power on the alpha frequency band (8-13 Hz) at the O or P electrode position, with condition:

- Other rhythm in the same channel,

- PDR at different channels beside O and P,
- PDR peak to peak amplitude $> 1 \mu V$.

If all of the above mentioned conditions are met, then the background rhythm exists (value = 1), otherwise the existence is lacking.

2. Brainwave frequency

The frequency is calculated through the maximum peak frequency of power spectrum at the rhythm we want to analyze, where the peak frequency of the k rhythm (f_{pk_k}) expressed as:

$$f_{pk_k} = i_{pk_k} \times f_r ; k \in K; K = \{PDR, \beta\} \quad (2.1)$$

Where (i_{pk_k}) is the selected index of peak power that multiplied with frequency resolution (f_r). Frequency resolution is the sampling frequency (F_s) divided by the number of data points (N). In this classification the extracted features are the peak frequency of PDR and beta rhythm.

Figure 2. Data distribution of: (a) patient age group and (b) gender.

3. Frequency asymmetry

Frequency asymmetry represents the frequency imbalance between hemispheres, which is expressed by the absolute difference between the right and left frequencies.

4. Brainwave amplitude

Amplitude is the square root of the power. The peak to peak amplitude (A_{pp}) and power (P) relationship using the Welch method is stated as follows.

$$A_{pp} = 2 \left| \left(\frac{P}{0.4896} \right)^{1/2} \right| \quad (2.2)$$

5. Amplitude asymmetry

Asymmetry of amplitude represents the imbalance of amplitude between hemispheres, which is expressed by the absolute difference of the right and left amplitudes.

Table 1. Weight value for each feature adopting from [2] and [5].

Features	Threshold			
	W = 0	W = 1	W = 2	W = 3
PDR existence	exist			lack
PDR frequency	$z \geq 9$	$8 < z < 9$	$6 \leq z \leq 8$	$z < 6$

PDR frequency asymmetry	$z < 0.5$	$0.5 \geq z > 1$	$1 \geq z > 2$	$z \geq 2$
PDR amplitude	$z < 100$	$100 \geq z > 130$	$z \geq 130$	
PDR amplitude asymmetry	$z < 50$	$50 \geq z > 60$	$60 \geq z > 80$	$z \geq 80$
APG	$z < 40$	$40 \geq z > 60$	$z \geq 60$	
Beta amplitude	$z \leq 50$	$50 > z > 100$	$z \geq 100$	
Beta amplitude asymmetry	$z < 50$	$50 \geq z > 60$	$60 \geq z > 80$	$z \geq 80$
% Existence of theta	$z = 0$	$0 > z > 5$	$5 \geq z > 50$	$z \geq 50$
% Existence of delta	$z = 0$	$0 > z > 5$	$5 \geq z > 50$	$z \geq 50$

6. APG

The anterior-posterior gradient represents the background rhythm ratio to the spatial resolution between the front and back region. APG is stated as follows.

$$APG = \left(1 - \frac{\bar{P}_{ant}}{\bar{P}_{ant} + \bar{P}_{pos}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (2.3)$$

Where \bar{P}_{ant} represent average power of anterior channel and \bar{P}_{pos} is average power of posterior region. The anterior channel consists of Fp1, Fp2, F7, F8, F3, and F4, the posterior channel consists of T5, T6, P3, P4, O1, and O2.

7. Existence percentage

Representing the percentage of the appearance of a rhythm on the overall data if its existence is sufficient. The existence percentage was calculated on theta and delta rhythms by comparing the peak power of the rhythm with the total power. The existence is sufficient if it meets the condition theta amplitude $> 15 \mu V$ and delta rhythm amplitude $> 25 \mu V$.

8. Total weight

Total weight is the sum of the weights of each of the features previously calculated which are presented in table 1.

2.3 Classification

The result of quantitative parametric calculation would be the input feature for classifier. The class group divided into normal and abnormal EEG (see figure 3). The classifier in this study was a discriminant analysis.

Figure 3. Block diagram algorithm to classify EEG normality and abnormality.

Discriminant analysis is a statistical classification method to find a linear combination of features to distinguish between two or several groups of phenomena [12]. The form of the separator function between classes of linear discriminant analysis (LDA) is a straight line. While in quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA), the form of separator is quadratic so that the form function for separate the class is curve.

2.4 Algorithm Perform Evaluation

Evaluation of algorithm perform is carried out using 10-fold cross validation with 130 normal and abnormal data. Then the result of accuracy of the data are calculated with formula:

$$\%Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \times 100\% \quad (2.4)$$

The balance between false positive and false negative is important in this analysis so that the evaluation of classification performance is not enough to be presented with accuracy. Therefore, it is necessary to assess performance for each target, both normality and abnormality. The sensitivity percentage is calculated to determine the significant algorithm in classifying abnormalities with the equation:

$$\%Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \times 100\% \quad (2.5)$$

Contrary to sensitivity, specificity is the ratio of the true value of normal class compared to the total normal data analysed. The purpose of the assessment is able to find out the level of algorithm performance in recognizing the normal class. The specificity percentage can be stated as follow.

$$\%Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \times 100\% \quad (2.6)$$

Where TP is true positive, TN is true negative, FP is false positive, and FN is false negative.

3. Result

3.1 Overall performance of DA classifier

The result of the accuracy calculation for discriminant analysis classifier with some type discriminant functions were shown in figure 4. Based on the produced accuracy percentage, the best result for DA was obtained from the one using linear type discriminant, which was 78.64%.

Figure 4. Performance algorithm of each type discriminant to determine EEG abnormality using discriminant analysis

3.2 Classifier performance using features from data fraction

This section wants to know whether the classification result would be different if it was performed to some different length of the raw data. Various data length divided into 4, dataset A, B, C, and D. Dataset A was raw EEG data with all length data. Dataset B was raw data obtained in the first, middle, and the end of five minutes. Dataset C was raw data obtained in the first, middle, and the end of one minute. The dataset D was a 5 minutes data that was manually selected with taking into account the best PDR existence value. The performance result of each dataset was represented in table 2.

Table 2. Performance accuracy in each dataset and discriminant type.

Discriminant type	Accuracy (%)							
	Dataset A	Dataset B			Dataset C			Dataset D
		early	mid	end	early	mid	end	
Linear	78.46	75.38	75.38	74.62	73.08	70.77	73.08	80.77
Quadratic	71.54	68.46	75.38	62.31	63.08	67.69	64.62	75.38

3.3 DA Performance in specific abnormal data

In the previous section, accuracy performance has been measured in the general cases of abnormalities with the best accuracy results of 78.46%. This section classification performance was measured with the abnormal data that was being separated based on the certain cases. There are 4 categories, abnormality for epilepsy, seizure, slowing background, and others. The classification was performed by using DA classifier with a linear type discriminant. The best accuracy result was 85.33% for classification of background slowing. The highest sensitivity was 64.52% in the epilepsy cases and the best specificity was 93.85% in the seizure (see figure 5).

Figure 5. Performance algorithm of each classifier to determine EEG abnormality.

4. Discussion

LDA is a classifier type that has been used several times in the previous study related to normal or abnormal classification of EEG data [9], [10]. When compared to power statistical features per frequency band in the previous studies, the results of using visual adoption features in the LDA classifier turned out to be slightly better at distinguishing the normalities or abnormalities in the awake patient EEG.

The feature extraction from t minutes data gave a better classification result than the one with less minute data analysis. The 5 minutes data fraction still gave the better result than 1 minute data fraction, especially for quadratic discriminant type. It could be concluded that the classification of normal and abnormal impression of the entire time could not only be represented with 1 minute fraction assessment. At least, it takes from 5 minutes data fraction to produce a better classification result.

According to table 2, it was observed that the results of the accuracy performance on the manually selected 5 minutes fraction data turned out to be better than the accuracy of the analysis on the t minutes data. This is because by making a manual determination, analysis for certain undesirable event such as artefact or the alertness of the patient during measurement could be avoided. So, the better perform result could be obtained. In the other words, the effect of manually selecting data has contributed to improve the performance of the EEG signal reading algorithm.

According to the result in figure 5, it showed that accuracy value in general for all cases has increased compare to the abnormal data classification without categorization. If it was assessed according to sensitivity and specificity performance, an increase in the accuracy value occurred because of the high value of specificity. It means the algorithm ability to recognize normal data contribute greatly to increase the accuracy value. However, the percentage of algorithm performance in a specific recognizing for LDA classifier was 64.52%. But it is not adequate with the value of its specificity. However, the potential to increase sensitivity still could be improved by adding the number of dataset for each case in the subsequent studies.

Ideally, the algorithm should have a high accuracy with a balance of sensitivity and specificity value. Thus, the algorithm could correctly recognize the normality and abnormality of EEG signal [12]. Whereas the evaluation algorithm performance have been conducted in this study, if identification is carried out on abnormal signal in general, LDA will give a higher sensitivity

percentage than when it is used for classification in the specific abnormality cases. On the other hand, the specificity for the introduction of normal signal data with abnormal populations is generally lower than the average percentage compared to some specific abnormalities.

Actually, there are potential that the algorithm can recognize the cases of special abnormalities, but it needs optimization in terms of feature quantitating and classifier training. It could add graphoelement recognition in the mechanism on the specific case in the feature quantization. The amount of disturbing artefact is one of the most effecting factor in this algorithm. There is one function that could eliminate artefact by identifying artefact on each quantization segment. The segmentation has been performed stationary with data length of 5 seconds. If there is an artefact detected in this 5 seconds segment, then the signal parameter calculation results in the segment are not included. In fact, not all segments contain artefacts. It could be that some of the signals deleted from the calculation are important information that needs to be analysed. So, it is suggested in future studies to pay more attention to this by implementing an adaptive segmentation. Adaptive segmentation is a method of separating signals into smaller fractions with non-stationary length data. The signal separation is based on the certain parameters, such as artefacts. It is expected that if the segmentation is conducted adaptively, the removal of artefacts could be more specific so that the missing of important information could be minimized.

5. Conclusion

The algorithm has a good performance that could distinguish normal and abnormal EEG signal up to 78.46%. The time fraction variation also gave impact in the algorithm performance. When the classification was conducted full automatically in the entire time signal, it gave the best performance result, compared to the time fraction 1 or 5 minutes. The EEG abnormality classification algorithm has potential to be applied in the cases of more specific abnormalities, especially in epilepsy that had 64.52% value of sensitivity with LDA.

6. References

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